

WORLD'S LARGEST MANDALAS

FROM MANIPUR AND CARL JUNG'S ARCHETYPE OF THE SELF

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MANDALA is generally considered as a geometric representation of the cosmology, administrative model (metaphorically) of the ancient Southeast Asia and the nature of mind or psyche. In the words of Carl Jung, "Mandala means 'circle' in the ordinary sense of the word. In the sphere of religious practices and in psychology it denotes circular images, which are drawn, painted, modelled, or danced. Plastic structure of this kind are to be found, for instance, in Tibetan Buddhism, and as dance figures these circular patterns occur also in Dervish monasteries. As psychological phenomena they appear spontaneously in dreams, in certain states of conflict, and in cases of schizophrenia. Very frequently they contain a quaternity or a multiple of four, in the form of cross, a star, a square, an octagon, etc." He interprets Mandala as "the psychological expression of the totality of the self". He describes "the

Self" as "the archetype of wholeness". To understand Jungian archetype of the Self; we need first, a brief sketch of his definition of psyche. For Jung psyche is the total personality – an individual's thoughts, emotions, behaviors and feelings. Jung believed in the continuous evolution of our consciousness towards the limitless extent. This evolution is extremely slow and laborious process, and takes millions of years to reach the civilized state. Although the development of our consciousness since the invention of writing, about 400 BC, seems to be considerable, Jung believed that it is still far from complete. He said that indefinitely large areas of our mind are still remained in darkness. So he rejected the school of thought which denies the existence of the unconscious. He concluded that those who deny the existence of the unconscious are those who assume "our knowledge of the psyche to be complete, with nothing left for further discoveries." So he divided psyche into separate but interacting levels. In order to understand the contents of the levels of Jungian

psyche, we first need to look into some of his key-terms: ego, persona, personal unconscious, collective unconscious, archetype, shadow, anima and animus, and self to name a few.

EGO is the conscious aspect of a person. Although it is known as the centre of our consciousness, ego knows only its own contents, not the other levels of psyche – unconscious and its contents. Persona indicates our outward personality like the mask worn by actors to indicate the role they played. In the words of Jung, "Fundamentally the persona is nothing real: it is a compromise between individual and society as to what a man should appear to be. He takes a name, earns a title, exercises a function, he is this and that. In a certain sense all this is real, yet in relation to the essential individuality of the person concerned it is only a secondary reality, a compromise formation, in making which others often have a great share than he. The persona is a semblance, a two-dimensional reality, to give it a nick

name.” The next level of Jungian psyche is the Personal Unconscious. It is a psyche below the threshold of sensation or consciousness. Its contents are the personal experience we have acquired during our lifetime as well as all things discarded, disused, worthless, forgotten, and repressed by our ego, but are “capable of becoming conscious.”

IN addition to our immediate consciousness (i.e., empirical psyche or ego) and personal unconscious, (i.e., repressed or forgotten contents) Jung discovered that there exists a collective unconscious, “a psychic system of a collective, universal, and impersonal nature which is identical in all individuals”. He said that this collective unconscious is an inborn pattern of our behavior which is not developed individually but is inherited from our history and from the “remotest times”. This level of psyche consists of “preexistent thought forms called archetypes, which give form to certain psychic material which then enters the conscious.” This deeper unconscious level manifests itself in universal archaic images expressed in dreams, religions, beliefs, myths and fairytales. In simple term archetypes are the ancient or archaic images that derive from the collective unconscious. He further continued that the search into the unconscious involves confronting the shadow, which is man’s hidden nature; the anima, a hidden feminine archetype in men; animus, a hidden masculine archetype in women; and beyond, the archetype of meaning. This collective unconscious, which unknowingly shape and mold our everyday thinking, is what Jung called as archetypes. Jung grasped the notion that the similarity between religious symbols and myths in various human cultures is influenced by the archetypes.

Self is the physiological integration of all the opposite levels of psyche. It comprises the totality of the psyche together, i.e. conscious and unconscious. Self could only be realized through what Jung called individuation, a process by which unconscious is brought into consciousness by method of active imagination (i.e., a sequence of fantasies produced by deliberate concentration), dreams (i.e., in the dream, our psyche speaks in images, and gives expression to instincts, which derive from the most primitive levels of nature) or free association, thus enlarging the scope of one’s personality.

IN his study of the unconscious processes at work in dreams, Jung said that, “The symbols of the process of individuation that appear in dreams are images of an archetypal nature which depict the centralizing process or the production of a new centre of personality.” He called this centre as “the Self”. He continued, “The Self is not only the centre (of the total personality), but also the whole circumference which embraces both conscious and unconscious; it is the centre of this totality, just as the ego is the centre of consciousness.” In simple term the Self is expressed by distinctive symbolic images called mandala. Jung chose the term “mandala” because it represents, “Formation; Transformation, Eternal Mind’s eternal recreation. And that it is the self, the wholeness of the personality, which if all goes well is harmonious, but which cannot tolerate self-deception... the mandala is the center. It is the exponent of all paths. It is the path to the center, to individuation.”

ALTHOUGH mandalas are widely found in every culture, the best and most significant mandalas, according to Jung, are found in the sphere of Tibetan Buddhism, in

which the mandala embraces the most sacred significance. The importance and significance of the eastern mandala symbols, in particular the Himalayan mandala, is well expressed in his book, *Psychology and Alchemy*, as follows: “The Eastern mandalas used in ceremonial are figures fixed by tradition; they may be drawn or painted or, in certain special ceremonies, even represented plastically. In 1938, I had the opportunity, in the monastery of Bhutia Busty, near Darjeeling, of talking with a Lamaic rimpoché, Lingdam Gomchen by name, about the *khilkor* or mandala. He explained it as a *dmigs-pa* (pronounced “migpa”), a mental image which can be built up only by a fully instructed lama through the power of imagination. He said that no mandala is like any other, they are all individually different. Also, he said, the mandalas to be found in monasteries and temples were of no particular significance because they were external representations only. The true mandala is always an inner image, which is gradually built up through (active) imagination, at such times when psychic equilibrium is disturbed or when a thought cannot be found and must be sought for, because it is not contained in holy doctrine.” Jung concluded that these Eastern symbols originated in dreams and visions, and were not invented by some Mahayana Church father.

BUT nevertheless there are various conventional types of Buddhist mandala fixed by traditions as stated above. The basic mandala motif found in many eastern traditions is a square with four cardinal gates or directions and eight lotus petals motif which commonly appear in the centre. The mandalas are painted on paper, cloth, wall and sand and carved on stone and built in the form of stupa or ground-plan of temples as in the case of Borobudur in Central

Fig 1. Maklang mandala

Java, Indonesia and Boudhanath Stupa in Kathmandu, Nepal. But one of the most intense archaeological discoveries in recent years that could redefine the history of eastern thought and tradition of mandala is the discovery of six giant mandalas in the valley of Manipur captured by Google Earth imagery.

LOCATED in the paddy field in the west of Imphal, the capital

of Manipur, the Maklang geoglyph (fig 1) is perhaps the world's largest mandala built entirely of mud. The site wasn't discovered until 2013 as its whole structure could only be visible via Google Earth satellite imagery. The whole paddy field, locally known as Bihu Loukon, is now protected and announced as historical monument and site by the government of Manipur in the same year. The site is situated 12

km aerial distance from Kangla with the GPS coordinates of 24° 48' N and 93° 49' E. It covers a total area of around 224,161.45 square meters. This square mandala has four similar protruding rectangular 'gates' in the cardinal directions guarded each by similar but smaller rectangular 'gates' on the left and right. Within the square there is an eight petalled flower or rayed-star, recently called as Maklang 'Star fort' by the locals,

in the centre covering a total area of around 50,836.66 square meters.

ANOTHER similar eight-petalled flower or rayed-star shaped earthwork (fig 2) is reported from Sekmai, 17.69 km aerial distance from Kangla with the GPS coordinates of 24° 58' N and 93° 53' E. It is located on western bank of the Sekmai River. It covers a total area of around 65,144.53 square meters. It is encircled by an earthwork that runs about 1.86 km.

ACCORDING to Jung the Archetypal square i.e. squaring the circle of the mandala is a symbol which is “one of the most important motifs in the objectivation of unconscious images”, which is “a mean of protecting the centre of the personality from being drawn out and from being influenced from outside.” The archetypal four cardinal gates, according to Jung, symbolize the parts, qualities, and aspects of the One. For example: four directions; four seasons; four elements; and four temperament; and in Buddhism the Four Noble Truths. The eight rayed star within the square may be used to symbolize the Noble Eightfold Path or the eight spoke Dharma Wheel. According to Jung, “The mandalas used in ceremonial are of great significance because their centres usually contain one of the highest religious figures: either Shiva himself – often in the embrace of Shakti – or the Buddha, Amitabha, Ava-lokiteshvara, or one of the great Mahayana teachers, or simply the *dorje*, symbol of all the divine forces together, whether creative or destructive.”

THE discovery of other four giant mandalas in the valley of Manipur is also made with Google Earth. The four giant mandalas, viz., Heikakmapal mandala (fig 3), Phurju twin mandalas (fig 4 & 5) and

Fig 2. Sekmai Mandala

Fig 3. Heikakmapal Mandala

Fig 4. & 5. Phurju Twin Mandalas

Sagolmang mandala (coined for the purpose of this article) are located on the western bank of the Iril River. The mandala at Heikakmapal Khabam paddy field is situated 14.20 km aerial distance from Kangla with the GPS coordinates of 24° 54' 35.7' N and 94° 02' 35.9' E in between the main Keibi road, also known as Lairen Lamkhai in the early period, in the west and the Iril River in the east and Loushangkhong road in the north. The villages surrounding the mandala are Heikakmapal Awang (northern) and Heikakmapal Makha (southern). The villages are mainly inhabited by five main extended families of Ongnam, Laishram, Yambem, Keisham and Ahanthem clans. The name of the village and the paddy field is derived from the Heikak *pat* or wetland, situated on the western side of the main road and on the eastern foothill of Yembung Chingdon. The Mandala covers a total area of around 122,231.72 square meters. It is encircled by an earthwork that runs about 1.64 km. It is entirely built of mud same as

the above Maklang mandala. It has the archetypal protruding gates in the cardinal direction. According to the memory of the inhabitants of the village there used to be a ditch surrounding the whole earthworks. Some of the remnants of the ditch of around 16.5 meters width are still there in the surroundings of the mandala. It seems that the earthworks

were raised by the mud collected from these ditches (fig 6). The remnants of the earthwork are around 8 meters in length and around 1.5 meter in height in general. In the disturbed area the earthwork is around 6 ft width and 1 foot high. Interestingly, each 12 pointed corners of the mandala have a circle of around 30 feet diameter (fig 7). The present

Fig 7. (Heikakmapal mandala)

inhabitants of Heikakmapal do not have any specific lore and tradition connected with the mandala.

According to the 1951 census the population of this village was only 135 persons and the number of houses was only 29. The local simply call it as *pali* meaning earthwork.

2.55 km aerial distance north from the Heikakmapal mandala, there is twin mandalas at Phurju paddy field. (Phurju was the name of the department dealing for the welfare of handicapped and disabled subjects of the erstwhile kingdom of Manipur. As the name suggest this place was granted as paddy field to this department). The first Phurju mandala is situated in the south with the GPS coordinates of 24° 55' N and 94° 02' E and the second Phurju mandala (fig 5) is situated in the north with GPS coordinates of 24° 56' N and 94° 02' E, on the bank of the same Iril River. The twin mandalas are intersected by the Tiger Camp hill (according to the locals Samom Leikai was renamed as Tiger Camp after 1940s communist movement in Manipur.) The first Phurju mandala covers a total area of around 117,516.80 square meters. It is encircled by an earthwork that runs about 1.62 km. The second

Fig 8. Sagolmang Mandala

mandala covers a total area of around 117,466.37 square meters. It is encircled by an earthwork that runs about 1.62 km. Both mandalas have the four identical cardinal gates. The structure, earthwork and ditches are all identical with the above Heikakmapal Mandala. The earthwork of the second twin

mandala is around 16ft wide and around 4 feet to 6 feet high. Across the river there is a village called Lamboi Khul (literary means village of the monks). According to the memory of this village, Lamboi khul was so called because it was first settled by the monks. There is also another mandala (fig 8) at

Sekta Living Museum (Secondary Burial Site)

Fig 6. Ditch and earthwork (Heikakmapal Mandala)

Sagolmang, 3 km away from the twin mandala with GPS coordinates of 24° 55' N and 94° 01' E. It covers a total area of 120,083.91 square meters. It is encircled by an earthwork that runs about 1.61 km.

INTERESTINGLY, all the four identical mandalas are built at the meandering river valley of the Iril. Although no artifacts have yet been reported within the earthworks of the mandalas, many rich artifacts of historical importance are excavated from the eastern side of the Iril Rivers, few meters away from the Heikak mapal mandala, at Sekta village. In March and April 1991 Archaeology Survey of India and Manipur State Archeology excavated a mound at Sekta village and recovered a large number of secondary burial pots, copper burial masks with human skulls, porcelain wares and 'Buddhist' relic caskets. The excavated site is now protected under the Manipur Ancient & Historical Monuments and Archaeological sites Remains Act and preserved as a living museum in 1996. The archaeological findings are not limited to Sekta.

The artifacts of tripod ware culture, including animal skeletons, were collected from Moirang Kampu Sajeb, 7 km south-west from Sekta, on the eastern bank of the same river in December 2012. The remnants of tripods and animal skeletons were acquired by the Department of History, Manipur University.

ALTHOUGH, so far, there are no literary sources known for the existence of the above mandalas, few myths and legends association with the Iril River can be mentioned here to broaden the scope in reconstructing the history of Iril River valley. Iril River was known as Linwai in archaic texts. Another

Remnants of a tripod (Moirang Kampu Sajeb)

place associated with Iril River frequently mentioned in the archaic texts is “Awang Phat-alou Lai Makol”. It is sometime mentioned as the source or an important place on the bank of Iril River.

PHAT-ALOU is probably derived from the Tai or Shan term *Phra Alaong* meaning Bodhisattva in the Southeast Asian Buddhist traditions. In his classic book *The Life and Legend of Gaudama, the Buddha of the Burmese*, Paul Bigandet, a 19th century catholic missionary bishop in Burma, writes, “*Alaong* is a derivative from the verb *Loang*, which means to be in an incipient way, in a way of progression towards something more perfect. A Buddha is at first a being in a very imperfect state; but passing through countless existences, he frees himself, by a slow process, from some of his imperfections; he acquires merits which enable him to rise in the scale of progress, science, and perfection.” Buddhism was not unknown in Manipur is evidenced from the archaeological finds, like the 5’ 7” high parinirvana statue of Buddha at Ingourok, near Khurkhul Village, now worshiped as Mahadeva by the Meiteis, and the statue of Buddha at Kharam near Kajikhul village built by King Khagemba few meters away from the Maklang mandala. Besides the archaic literatures dealing with Sunyata or “emptiness doctrines” also shows that Buddhist philosophy was not foreign to Manipur. The archaic Meitei text *Khongchomnupi Nongkaron* writes, “the Kabos of the eastern country worship their god named **Phura** Lainingthou Senpi Kabo **Sendreng** (Buddha).” During the reign of Chingthangkhomba, two court scholars Nanda Haoiba and Rasananda Konsaba translated a Jataka story from Shan language to Manipuri under the title “**Aloang Nandakumar Laibu Ningba**” in 1787. The story tells how one Nandakumar

became *Aloang* or Bodhisattva.

ACCORDING to one legend the place “Phat-Aloang Lai Makol” was the place where Nongda Lairen Pakhangba, founder of the Ningthouja Dynasty, was taking refuge with his father Sendreng Pakhangba, after he was ousted from Kangla by the Khaba tribe. The land and river water dispute between the Khaba tribe and the Angom tribe, whose territory on the eastern side of the Imphal River led to the fetching of Poireiton, an immigrant from Kham Nung (the historic Kham Region of Tibet?) by the Khaba chief and Pakhangba by the Angom chief Pureiromba. After the defeat of Khaba and its ally Poireiton, Nongda

Lairen Pakhangba occupied Kangla and he established his dynasty of kings. Awang Phatlou or Phat-Aloang Lai Makol, as the name suggest, might be a Buddhist stronghold, since it is often associated with Eastern Buddhist terms, like Pakhangba, Sendreng and Phra Alaoung. The title Pakhangba, like the Burmese royal title *Alaung Phra* meaning *embryo* Buddha, was developed in the Meitei mythology in parallel with the Buddhist concept of realizing *sunyata* or emptiness or the throne of Enlightenment according to the old texts *Leithak-Leiharol* and *Leisemlon*. It is also a well known fact in Meitei tradition that Pakhangba as a god, whose *Cheng-hongba* or birthday was observed on the Buddha purnima day

■ Kāmadhātu ■ Rūpadhātu ■ Arūpadhātu

The plan of Borobudur took form of a Mandala, a model of universe in Hindu-Buddhist cosmology. It consists of three ascending realms, Kāmadhātu (the realm of desire), Rūpadhātu (the realm of form), and Arūpadhātu (the realm of formlessness).

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Kangla Paphal (18th - 19th century), Manipur
Courtesy: Mutua Bahadur & e-pao.net

every year in Manipur, is normally represented by coiled dragon biting its tail known as *paphal*.

ACCORDING to Carl Jung, the symbol of the snake or dragon biting its tail or Ouroboros is an allusion or basic old alchemical mandala. In his words, “The alchemists, who in their own way knew more about the nature of the individuation process than we moderns do, expressed this paradox through the symbol of the Ouroboros, the snake that eats its own tail. The Ouroboros has been said to have a meaning of infinity or wholeness... The Ouroboros is a dramatic symbol for the integration and assimilation of the opposite... This ‘feed-back’ process is at the same time a symbol of immortality, since it is said of the Ouroboros that he slays himself and brings himself to life, fertilizes himself and gives birth to himself. He symbolized the One, who proceeds from the clash of opposites.” Jung concluded that the aim of an individual is the realization of Self, the integration of all opposite aspects of psyche what he called it as the realization of innermost divine essence of man or the attainment of wholeness. And mandala (or *paphal* in Manipuri) is its visual representation.

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